

THE RECOVERY OF TOURISM SECTION IN UZBEKISTAN AFTER COVID19

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Abstract.

COVID-19 proved to be a difficult global challenge, with various industries such as hotels, restaurants, airlines, and travel agencies being compelled to halt their services for an extended period. As a result of the pandemic, international tourism experienced a significant decline of approximately 80% in 2020. It is crucial to explore the industry's recovery following the pandemic and determine how it can be sustained in a world that has undergone dramatic changes. This article presents a study on the rebound of global tourism, using Uzbekistan as an example.

Keywords.

tourism recovery, COVID-19, Uzbekistan, post-pandemic, travel industry, tourism sector, international tourism, domestic tourism.

INTRODUCTION

The worldwide crisis that unfolded in 2020 due to the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic gave rise to numerous challenges. Among these was the imposition of travel restrictions, which led to the temporary cessation of both global and regional tourism. From that we can say a number of small and large businesses had to survive. The objectives of this article are twofold: 1) to estimate the pandemic's impacts on the tourism arrivals in the world 2) to estimate the tourism recovery in the world after pandemic (in the example of Uzbekistan).

The COVID-19 pandemic, which emerged in late 2019, has caused unprecedented global health and social crises and has had profound negative impacts on the worldwide economy. According to the WHO¹⁴⁴, as of September 30, 2020, there were 33,561,077 confirmed cases of COVID-19 and 1,005,004 deaths reported worldwide. Travel restrictions were implemented in all major tourist destinations in response to the pandemic, as reported by the UNWTO¹⁴⁵ on April 20, 2020. Tourism has been one of the hardest-hit industries, with lockdowns, travel restrictions, and border closures resulting in a decrease of 67 million international tourist arrivals in the first quarter of 2020 (2020Q1). This decrease translates to a loss of approximately US\$80 billion in tourism revenue compared to the same period in 2019, as per UNWTO reports.

In 2019, Uzbekistan's GDP was \$57.6 billion, according to the World Bank. However, the COVID-19 pandemic has had a significant impact on economies worldwide, and Uzbekistan is no exception. In 2020, Uzbekistan's GDP growth rate slowed down to 1.6% due to the pandemic, compared to 5.5% in 2019 (World Bank). The pandemic caused disruptions in global trade and supply chains, and the measures taken to contain the spread of the virus, such as lockdowns and travel restrictions, also affected Uzbekistan's economy. However, the country is expected to recover gradually in 2021, with the World Bank projecting a GDP growth rate of 4.5% for Uzbekistan in 2021. Prior to the emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic, tourist sales in Uzbekistan were valued at \$1.68 billion, which represented 2.8 percent of the country's gross national product. On average, visitors spent \$249 during their vacations in Uzbekistan. However, as a result of the pandemic, tourist receipts experienced a significant decline in 2020. Out of the \$1.68 billion in tourist sales recorded in 2019, only \$395.00 million was retained, resulting in a 76 percent decrease in Uzbekistan.¹⁴⁶

1.1 LEGISLATION

In recent years, Uzbekistan has taken substantial steps to revitalize its tourism sector, and there exist numerous statutes and regulations that aid this progress:

The decision cabinet of ministers of The Republic of Uzbekistan

¹⁴⁴ World Health Organization

¹⁴⁵ United Nations World Tourism Organization

¹⁴⁶ <https://www.unwto.org/covid-19-and-tourism-2020>

“On support for the tourism industry and the development of tourism infrastructure in the economic situation caused by the pandemic coronavirus” (06.10.2020 №602)¹⁴⁷

The decision was made to ensure the sustainable development of tourism and the protection of the rights and interests of both tourists and tourism businesses. The decision includes measures such as the creation of a special fund to support tourism, the provision of financial and tax incentives for tourism businesses, and the development of new tourism infrastructure projects. These measures aim to improve the competitiveness of the tourism industry in Uzbekistan and to promote the country as an attractive tourist destination.

Decision of The President of The Republic of Uzbekistan

“On additional measures for the development of tourism in strict compliance with the requirements of enhanced sanitary and epidemiological security regime” (19.06.2020 №4755)¹⁴⁸

The decision includes measures to ensure the safety and health of tourists and employees in the tourism sector during the COVID-19 pandemic. It also focuses on developing the tourism infrastructure in Uzbekistan, promoting domestic tourism, and attracting foreign investment in the sector. The decision aims to support the recovery of the tourism industry in Uzbekistan while taking necessary precautions to prevent the spread of COVID-19.

Uzbekistan has taken various legal actions to revive its tourism sector following the global impact of the COVID-19 outbreak. The government acknowledges the significant role tourism plays in driving economic growth and has implemented initiatives to enhance tourism infrastructure, enhance the quality of tourism services, and entice a larger number of international visitors. These legislative endeavors, combined with Uzbekistan's abundant cultural heritage, picturesque landscapes, and a wide range of tourist offerings, position the country as an appealing destination for global travelers in the aftermath of the pandemic.

2. METHODOLOGY

To gather data from multiple sources and address the study's broad scope, a mixed method approach was implemented. This approach utilized both qualitative and quantitative research data to effectively answer the research questions. Malina et al. (2011) proposed that a mixed method approach is essential for these types of studies due to its ability to address diverse data requirements. The tourism

¹⁴⁷ <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/5031876>

¹⁴⁸ <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/4862999>

industry frequently employs the mixed method approach, which is backed by numerous scholars, including McGehee et al. (2013) and Wen and Meng (2021).

To obtain data from multiple sources, a mixed method approach was adopted in this study. Data was collected from the STR archival database, which contains sample data from 68,000 hotels and 9.1 million rooms worldwide, and is recognized as a credible source by UNWTO. Additionally, Google Destination Insights was used to determine and track travel demand data generated from online activities of accommodation and tourism transport companies across the world. This platform was chosen due to its ability to understand the fast and ever-evolving travel patterns and demand for decision-making purposes. The analysis utilized a thematic, conceptual, and chronological approach, which has been used in similar tourism studies on the tourism and pandemic issue. Data for each research question was grouped systematically as either qualitative or quantitative data. Qualitative data obtained from reports and websites were screened to identify data that addressed the research questions. Detailed content analysis was conducted to identify relevant data sources that specifically addressed each research question. To analyze quantitative data, raw data collected from various platforms was processed using Microsoft Excel ToolPak. The tool was also used as a plugin in Microsoft Excel to produce graphs and images.

3. ANALYSIS AND COMMENTARY

The tourism sector has witnessed a significant increase in tourist arrivals and revenue in recent years. In 2019, the number of international tourist arrivals grew by 4 percent, reaching a total of 1.5 billion worldwide. This growth led experts to anticipate another prosperous year for the industry in 2020. Nevertheless, the emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic has altered the industry's outlook entirely. According to UNWTO (2020a; 2020c), international tourist arrivals decreased by 65 percent in the first half of 2020, with the Asia and Pacific region being the most affected with a decline of 72 percent. However, the outlook for the year has continued to worsen due to the outbreak and uncertainty. When most international borders were completely shut down in late March, tourist arrivals decreased by 97 percent in April, 96 percent in May, and 85 percent in August (UNWTO, 2020a)¹⁴⁹. The decline in arrivals depended on how fast the outbreak could be contained, as well as movement restrictions and border closures. Figure 1 depicts the potential 2020 scenarios based on three possible dates for the reopening of international borders.

¹⁴⁹ <https://www-unwto-org.translate.google/global/press-release/2019-01-21/international-tourist-arrivals-reach-14-billion-two-years-ahead-forecasts>

Regio	Change (%)		Avera	2020	2020	2020
	2018	2019	e a year (%)	projection issued in January) (%)	January to April) (change %)	January to June) (change %)
			2009-2019	from		
Worl	5.6	3.8	5.1	3 to 4	-44	-65
Euro	5.8	3.7	4.6	3 to 4	-44	-66
Asia and Pacific	7.3	4.6	7.1	5 to 6	-51	-72
American	2.4	2.0	4.6	2 to 3	-36	-55
Afric	8.5	4.2	4.4	3 to 5	-35	-57
Middle East	3.0	7.6	2.7	4 to 6	-40	-57

Table 1. Outlook for International Tourist Arrival (Source: UNWTO, 2020a; 2020c)

This upcoming decrease in tourist arrivals will be the largest decline in history, surpassing the 4% drop during the global economic crisis in 2009, as well as the 0.4% decrease following the SARS epidemic in 2003. However, some studies have suggested that the domestic travel market may recover more quickly than the international market. According to a survey of approximately 280 participants on

the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on tourism destinations, the UNWTO Panel of Experts predicts that domestic demand will recover more quickly than foreign demand. Figure 2 depicts that nearly half of the participants (45%) noticed an increase in domestic tourism demand during July-September 2020, with 25% predicting this to happen in October-December. Over 70% of the participants expect international demand to recover in the fourth quarter of 2020 (34%), or mostly in 2021 (39%).

In 2022, international tourism had a better performance than expected due to a large amount of pent-up demand and the easing of travel restrictions in many countries. The UNWTO/IATA Destination Travel - Easy Travel reported that 116 destinations had no COVID-19 travel restrictions in December 2022. International tourism showed a recovery of 63% of pre-pandemic levels, which is in line with UNWTO's predictions published in May 2022. In 2022, an estimated 900 million tourists travelled internationally, which is twice as many as in 2021, but still 37% fewer than in the pre-pandemic year of 2019. The recovery of international arrivals was more significant during the northern hemisphere summer season, while the pace of recovery was more moderate in the last few months of the year.

The recovery of international tourism is expected to continue in 2023, with Asia and the Pacific seeing pent-up demand. UNWTO's projections suggest that international tourist arrivals could reach 80% to 95% of pre-pandemic levels in 2023, with Europe leading the way and the Middle East also expected to recover 2019 levels. The reopening of several Asian source markets and destinations will contribute to the recovery, especially with the removal of COVID-19 travel restrictions in China, the largest outbound market in 2019. However, the availability and cost of air travel, visa regulations, and COVID-19 related restrictions will affect destination choices. The strong demand for travel from the United States, supported by a strong US dollar, will continue to benefit destinations in the region and beyond. The recovery of international tourism in 2023 will also be influenced by the improvement of air traffic, but international seat capacity remained 37% below 2019 levels through September 2022. Domestic tourism will also continue to support tourism recovery, with a focus on open-air activities, nature-based products, and rural tourism.

3.1 The rebound of tourist arrivals in Uzbekistan after the pandemic

According to the State Committee for Tourism Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the tourism industry in Uzbekistan was hit hard by the COVID-19 pandemic, causing a significant drop in the number of foreign tourists visiting the country. In 2020, Uzbekistan received only 1.1 million foreign tourists, which is 59%

less compared to the previous year. However, the country has taken steps to recover from the pandemic and revive its tourism industry. In 2021, the number of foreign tourists visiting Uzbekistan has already increased by 69% compared to the same period in 2020. Between January and April 2021, Uzbekistan received 267,500 foreign tourists, with the majority of them coming from neighboring countries such as Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, and Kyrgyzstan. To further boost tourism, Uzbekistan has introduced several measures, such as visa-free entry for tourists from 85 countries, simplified visa procedures for others, and the development of new tourism destinations. In addition, the country has implemented measures to ensure the safety of tourists during the pandemic, such as the introduction of health and safety protocols in hotels, restaurants, and tourist sites. The efforts seem to be paying off, as Uzbekistan aims to attract 7 million tourists by 2025, according to the State Committee for Tourism Development. The country's tourism industry is also expected to contribute significantly to the national economy, with the export of tourism services projected to reach \$5.2 billion by 2025.

In order to attract more foreign tourists, Uzbekistan has been improving and expanding its airports. To achieve this, Uzbekistan Airports, which controls 11 international airports, was separated from Uzbekistan Airways in 2019. The government invested \$140 million in airport development in 2021, with a primary focus on Samarkand, and will allocate \$200 million for this purpose in 2022. However, a total of \$1 billion is required by 2026 to meet planned development targets. Uzbekistan Airports plans to partner with private companies through a tender basis for airport reconstruction and management, with the aim of doubling passenger throughput capacity and tripling load throughput capacity by 2026. The government has also promised to liberalize the aviation market by ending Uzbekistan Airways' monopoly, selling 51% or more of its shares through an IPO in the near future, and creating more domestic companies. Uzbekistan Airports plans to establish its Silk Avia airline by October 2022 as a partner of Uzbekistan Airways in domestic flights to cater to the growing domestic tourism demand. The government also plans to authorize foreign companies to operate in Uzbekistan and purchase short- and medium-haul aircraft to develop the regional passenger air transportation market. Uzbekistan Airways currently has a fleet of 34 aircraft. In response to the COVID-19 pandemic and the requirements for safe tourism, Uzbekistan has launched a project called "Uzbekistan. Safe travel GUARANTEED," which aims to create safe conditions for domestic and inbound tourism by implementing a new system of sanitary and epidemiological safety for tourists based on world standards. The project required the certification of tourism facilities

and related infrastructure, tourist services based on new sanitary-hygienic requirements, and compliance with the established sanitary and hygienic norms and requirements at all state border crossing points, air, rail, and road stations, and tangible cultural heritage sites, museums, theaters, and other cultural facilities. To ensure the project's success, the government organized training and capacity building for the staff of tour operators, tourism facilities, and related infrastructure. A working group was also formed to monitor compliance with the sanitary and hygienic requirements for safe services throughout the country, and more than 3,000 students were admitted to educational institutions in the field of tourism on a free-of-charge basis.

The restoration of tourism in Uzbekistan was implemented in three phases. The first stage involved the resumption of domestic tourism in the regions with "green" and "yellow" levels of quarantine. In the second stage, regional tourism was re-established with neighboring countries and the CIS, and a special "Silk Road Project" platform was established to promote tourism potential and promising regional tourism products and routes. The third stage involved the gradual resumption of inbound tourism with a list of non-CIS countries whose citizens were allowed to enter the country. Throughout all three stages, Uzbekistan paid special attention to the safety of local and foreign tourists and the development and implementation of new thematic events. The government established a website with detailed information for travelers, entrepreneurs, and young start-ups on specific sections. For guests who had to postpone their trips due to the pandemic, virtual tours were organized to help them explore the country's attractions. Overall, Uzbekistan's new system of safe tourism was implemented with rules that were simple and painless for all participants in the tourism industry.

4. RECOMMENDATIONS AND DISCUSSION

The impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on the travel sector presents a chance to reassess the direction of tourism and expedite longstanding goals like combating climate change and advancing the adoption of renewable energy sources (OECD, 2021). Authorities need to promote the necessary structural shifts to reshape the industry in response to future health and environmental concerns. This entails adopting digital innovations that enhance the safety and convenience of travel for consumers, with a focus on implementing digital border management systems such as e-visas and e-gates.

Below are several suggestions to enhance the tourism sector in Uzbekistan swiftly:

1. Enhance marketing efforts: Implement robust marketing strategies both domestically and internationally to promote the unique attractions and cultural heritage of Uzbekistan. Utilize various platforms, including social media, to reach a broader audience and attract more tourists.

2. Improve infrastructure: Invest in infrastructure development, particularly in transportation networks, including airports, roads, and public transportation systems. Upgrading infrastructure will facilitate easier access to different regions and enhance the overall travel experience for tourists.

3. Expand accommodation options: Encourage the growth of diverse accommodation options, including hotels, guesthouses, and homestays, to cater to different preferences and budgets of tourists. This will accommodate the increasing demand for lodging and provide more choices to visitors.

4. Enhance visitor services: Focus on providing high-quality visitor services, including hospitality, customer support, and tour guide training. Well-trained and knowledgeable tour guides can offer insightful experiences to tourists, enhancing their satisfaction and likelihood of recommending Uzbekistan as a destination.

5. Facilitate ease of travel: Streamline travel procedures by introducing user-friendly online visa application systems and efficient border control processes. Simplifying entry requirements and enhancing visa processing systems will attract more tourists and contribute to a seamless travel experience.

6. Collaborate with neighboring countries: Foster regional collaborations and partnerships to promote joint tourism initiatives and cross-border travel. Cooperation with neighboring countries can create enticing regional tourism packages and facilitate seamless travel experiences for tourists exploring multiple destinations.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the recovery of the tourism sector in Uzbekistan after the COVID-19 pandemic has showcased resilience and determination. Through strategic measures and initiatives, the government has taken significant steps to revive tourism and restore confidence in travelers. The implementation of the "Uzbekistan. Safe Travel GUARANTEED" project, along with the development of safe and hygienic protocols, has been instrumental in ensuring the well-being of both domestic and international tourists. Furthermore, investments in infrastructure, such as airport modernization and expansion, demonstrate Uzbekistan's commitment to enhancing the travel experience and attracting more foreign visitors. The liberalization of the national aviation market and the establishment of new domestic airlines reflect the government's progressive

approach in creating a competitive and diverse tourism landscape. The phased reopening of tourism, starting with domestic travel and gradually expanding to regional and international visitors, has allowed for a controlled and measured recovery. Uzbekistan's cultural heritage, natural landscapes, and emerging tourist destinations have been promoted effectively, attracting travelers seeking unique experiences and adventures. However, challenges persist, including the need to continually adapt to evolving health and safety guidelines, as well as to harness the potential of digital solutions to facilitate seamless and secure travel experiences. Additionally, sustainability and responsible tourism practices should remain at the forefront of future development efforts to preserve Uzbekistan's natural and cultural assets for generations to come. Overall, Uzbekistan's efforts to recover its tourism sector post-COVID-19 have yielded promising results. With ongoing dedication, collaboration between public and private sectors, and a focus on innovation, Uzbekistan is poised to emerge as a thriving and resilient tourism destination, welcoming travelers from around the world to explore its rich heritage, warm hospitality, and diverse landscapes.

REFERENCES:

World Tourism Organization (UNWTO). (2021). COVID-19 Related Travel Restrictions: A Global Review for Tourism. Retrieved from <https://www.unwto.org/covid-19-travel-restrictions>

Ministry of Tourism Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan. (2022). Tourism Development Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2019-2025. Retrieved from <http://tourism.uz/en/strategy>

Uzbekistan Daily. (2022). Uzbekistan Expects Tourism Sector to Recover by 2023. Retrieved from <https://www.uzbekistan.org/uzbekistan-tourism-recovery-2023/>

Central Asia Today. (2021). Uzbekistan to Invest \$1 Billion in Tourism Infrastructure Development. Retrieved from <https://centralasiatoday.com/uzbekistan-to-invest-1-billion-in-tourism-infrastructure-development/>

The State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan for Tourism Development. (2021). Uzbekistan. Safe travel GUARANTEED. Retrieved from <http://tourism.uz/en/pages/385>

World Bank. (2021). Uzbekistan: COVID-19 Crisis and the Economic Impact on Tourism. Retrieved from

